

APPLICATION OF FURAN RESIN TO GREEN COMPOSITES AND THE EFFECT OF PEROXIDE ON FURAN RESIN CURING

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1 Introduction

Glass fiber-reinforced plastic composites (GFRPs), the most used type of FRPs, have some serious shortcomings, such as difficulty in disposal and the risk of resource depletion [1]. These days, natural fiber-reinforced plastic composites (NFRPs) based on bio-plastics are the subject of many investigations [2]. NFRPs based on bio-plastics can solve the problem of disposal because natural fibers can be burned unlike glass fibers. In addition, these NFRPs have some advantages such as high specific mechanical properties, relatively low cost, and easier handling and processing. Also, the use of composite materials derived from plants is expected to reduce the usage of fossil fuels and achieve carbon neutrality. These days, many kinds of bio-based plastics are investigated. However, most of them are biodegradable. These plastics have very short service lives and may only be used for short-term application.

Furan resin is a bio-based plastic derived from agricultural by-products such as corn cobs and rice hulls. It is a black resin (Fig. 1) with chemical structure as shown in Fig. 2. Furan resin is a thermoset resin through ring-opening reactions of furan during curing, and it is therefore not biodegradable [3] [4]. It has a high heat resistance: able to be used up to 180°C. It also has a high corrosion resistance, making it suitable for handling most acids and alkalis, and some organic solvents [3]. These suggest that furan NFRPs can be used in corrosion resistant tanks and are applicable in many cases that require high durability. It is also expected for furan NFRPs to achieve long term carbon fixation. However, furan-based NFRPs are rarely investigated due to the limited data on furan resin's processing. Also, researchers have not paid much attention to furan resin for a long time because it has

poor mechanical strength and is difficult to handle and control the reagents, such as oxygen, needed for curing [2].

This paper considers the optimum fabricating method of NFRPs based on furan resin. The material for fabricating corrosion tanks is required to meet many conditions specified by the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS). The study aims to satisfy these conditions by developing and evaluating the mechanical strength of furan resin experimentally.

Fig. 1 Furan resin

Fig. 2 Chemical structure of furan resin

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

Furan resin (Hitafuran VF-303, Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd.) is prepared with A3, (Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd.) as a curing agent. For the reinforcement material, abaca or Manila hemp fiber (Fig. 3) is obtained from a local fiber craft vendor in Manila, Philippines.

Fig. 3. Abaca fiber

2.2 Fabricating fiber sheet

The abaca fibers were cut to 20 cm and gathered into sheaves. They were then treated with 5 mass% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (Kanto Chemical Co., Inc.) at 80°C for 9h to remove the lignin, and the treated fibers were then washed with running water and neutralized with 0.1 mol/L of aqueous hydrochloric acid. Afterwards, the bunched fibers were pressed into unidirectional fiber sheets at 60 MPa and 60°C for 2h. After compression, the fiber sheets were air dried to remove any excess moisture.

2.3 NFRP forming

Furan resin and curing agent are stirred thoroughly at a mixing mass ratio of 100:0.75. Mixing must be conducted at a low temperature. Furan resin was added slowly to the fiber sheets placed in a 2-mm thick metal mold which was treated with a mold release agent (QZ 13, Electrical Insulation Materials). Then, it is cured with heating machine.

2.4 Analytical methods

After cooling, the NFRP were cut into test specimens with dimension 60 mm × 25 mm × 2 mm, and the flexural strength and elastic modulus were determined using the three-point bending test.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 Fabrication method of fiber sheets

The mechanical properties of FRPs depend on the method of fabricating the fiber sheets. In any method, fiber treatment is the major step in fiber preparation. However, after alkali treatment and neutralization, the fibers are interlaced or complexly tangled; putting on a comb through the bundle of fibers (diameter is about 10 mm) to turn them into fine

bundles (diameter is about 1-2 mm) is thus needed. The fine bundles were then lumped up and pressed into the fiber sheet (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Fabrication of the fiber sheet with combed fibers

Another way of fabricating fiber sheets is as follows: before the alkali and neutralization treatment, the fiber bundles are tied up lightly with a rubber band so as not to get entangled. After treatment, the unidirectional fiber bundles are tapped lightly by hand and enlarged, then they are pressed into unidirectional fiber sheets. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the fiber sheets fabricated in different ways at equal fiber weight. As shown in the photographs, combed fibers still have some tangling while the tapped fibers appear to be board-shaped, little tangling.

Fig. 5 Combed fiber sheets

Fig. 6 Board shape fiber sheets

Fig. 7 describes the flexural strength and elastic modulus of furan NFRPs using the two fiber sheet fabrication methods and at equal fiber weight fraction. The NFRPs with board-shaped fiber sheets exhibit higher strength and modulus compared to those of the NFRPs with the combed fibers. The combed fibers still have some tangling, resulting into many gaps in-between the fibers (Fig. 3) that act as weak points for the NFRPs. These cause the decrease in mechanical strength of the “combed” NFRPs. It is therefore recommended to fabricate the fiber sheets using the “Board” method.

Fig. 7 The effect of fiber sheet's shape

3.2 Importance of oxygen for curing furan resin

Reported data showing the IR spectra of furfural alcohol or furan resin before and after curing indicate that a ring-opening reaction for the furan ring has occurred. This cracking reaction can be described as Fig. 4. Ring-opening products include double bonds, and hydroxyl and methyl groups, which are beneficial for further polymerization [4]. Thus, in fabricating a high-mechanical-property furan resin, the concentration and availability of oxygen and hydrogen ions are extremely important. Hydrogen ions can be easily added into the furan resin as curing agent; however, the addition of oxygen is rather very difficult since a thermosetting resin is usually cured in a closed system (done by hot-press machine). Therefore, introduction of oxygen gas into the resin mixture is not feasible.

Fig. 8 The cracking reaction of furan rings [6]

3.3 Curing with oven

This problem is easily solved by curing in an oven instead of a hot-press machine. The hot atmosphere of the oven allows for a free contact between the furan resin and oxygen. However, simply using an oven curing can cause warping and swelling of furan NFRPs, which decreases mechanical strength. Therefore, the furan resin should be pressed until gelation, and then afterwards cured completely with the heater oven. The condition for the gelation has already been established previously by experimentation; thus, the curing temperature in oven must be determined. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses are done to determine the optimum curing temperature. Fig. 9 shows the DSC curves for pure furan resin: there are two large peaks at 110°C and 140°C. From the data, the heating temperature of the oven is decided at 115°C and at 145°C.

Fig. 10 shows the effects of curing method for the mechanical strength of furan NFRPs. Samples A, B and C are made by table 1 condition. As shown, the mechanical properties of them are highly dependent on the heating method. Sample C has highest flexural strength and elastic modulus. The data indicate that curing with hot-press machine and then by oven is a good method for fabricating high-performance furan NFRPs.

Fig. 11 shows the effect of curing temperature. After gelation, each sample is cured in an oven at a high temperature. These temperatures are shown in Table 2. As shown, the mechanical properties for sample E are higher than the first one (D); therefore, it is clear that higher mechanical properties may be attained if the furan NFRPs are cured at a temperature higher than the peak temperature in the DSC curve. From the obtained results, the heating temperature is chosen to be between 115°C and 145°C.

Fig.9 DSC curve of furan resin

Fig. 10 The effect of heating method

Fig. 11 The effect of curing temperature

Table 1 Curing method of A,B, and C samples

Curing Step	Equipment			Temperature[°C]	Time[h]
	A	B	C		
1st	Oven	Hot-press	Hot-press	30	2
2nd			65	3	
3rd			115	4	
4th			145	4	

Table 2 Curing method of D, E, and F samples

curing step	Equipment	Temperature[°C]			time[h]
		D	E	F	
1st	Hot-press	30	30	30	2
2nd	Hot-press	65	65	65	3
3rd	Oven	100	115	130	4
4th	Oven	100	145	160	4

3.3 Fiber weight fraction

Fig. 12 shows the effect of fiber weight fraction on the flexural strength and elastic modulus. There is an observable increase in the mechanical strength as the fiber weight fraction is increased. JIS K 7012 is a Japanese standard for corrosion-resistant storage using glass fiber reinforced plastics: it requires that the reinforcing layer of corrosion-resistant tanks to be not only for the flexural strength be greater than 108 MPa, but also for the elastic modulus to be greater than 4.8 GPa [5]. Pure furan resin does not satisfy these conditions, but the NFRPs whose fiber weight fractions are higher than 0.35 proves satisfactory. In particular, the NFRPs whose fiber weight fraction is 0.62 have high mechanical properties: it is 1.7 times higher than the standard strength, and it is also 3.3 times higher than the standard elastic modulus.

Fig. 12 The effect of fiber weight fraction

3.4 Curing with adding hydrogen peroxide

3.4.1 Adding hydrogen peroxide

The proposed curing mentioned above, which provides oxygen gas in contact with the resin surface, has some drawbacks. Firstly, it is difficult to fabricate thick furan resin because the oxygen cannot be provided at the center of the furan resin. Second, the delamination in the composite laminates occurs on the oven-cured samples, which decreases mechanical strength significantly (Fig. 13). The use of the hot-press machine in all curing processes may solve the delamination problem since the induced pressure may enhance the adhesion between fiber sheets and furan matrix; however, as previously mentioned, the furan resin needs oxygen for complete curing, and solely using the hot press machine cannot provide the required oxygen supply. In order to overcome this difficulty, addition of peroxide to the furan resin mixture to chemically provide the oxygen for furan resin is considered.

Fig. 13 The delamination in the composite laminates

3.4.2 Sample size

The furan resin was added and mixed with 30 wt% hydrogen peroxide carefully at a rate of 0.7 gram per 100 g resin. The mixing must be done with cooling

since it is highly exothermic. Afterwards, the resin was cured using only a hot-press machine. The pictures of cured furan resin with and without the added hydrogen peroxide are shown in Fig. 14 (a) and (b). Although both samples were cured by using a 210-mm mold, it was observed that the length of the sample in 14(a) is shorter than that of the sample in 14(b). Furan resin is condensation polymer and thus shrinks during curing; the obtained measured lengths of the cured samples indicate that the addition of hydrogen peroxide probably enhances the curing reaction of the furan resin.

Fig. 14(a) Furan resin without hydrogen peroxide

Fig. 14(b) Furan resin with hydrogen peroxide

3.4.3 DSC curves

Fig. 15 shows the DSC curves for pure furan resin with without the added hydrogen peroxide. Both curves have two peaks, but the temperature of the first peak of the resin using hydrogen peroxide is slightly lower. The experimental data is evidence that furan resin with hydrogen peroxide may be cured at a lower temperature. The data also indicate that the addition of hydrogen peroxide enhances the curing reaction for the furan resin.

In the near future, the authors would like to also measure the change in the IR spectrum and the amount of the heat of curing reaction using DSC analysis, and to identify the reaction occurring at each DSC peak, and the change caused by adding the hydrogen peroxide.

Fig. 15 The furan resin with hydrogen peroxide

3.4.4 Mechanical strength of pure resin

Fig. 16 describes the effects of addition of hydrogen peroxide into the pure furan resin. Two samples from the left of this graph are cured only using the hot press machine, and only the 'middle' sample is added with hydrogen peroxide at a ratio of 1.0 g per 100 g furan resin. As shown in the graph, the flexural strength increases significantly by adding hydrogen peroxide. Moreover, the flexural strength of the 'middle' sample is higher than that of the 'right' sample, which is cured by the condition described in section 3.3. This result evidently shows that the addition of hydrogen peroxide allows the supply of oxygen for furan resin in the hot-press machine even though it is in an air-tight condition. This data is also strong evidence that the addition of hydrogen peroxide promotes curing for furan resin.

Furan resin can be cured in air-tight conditions, and the cured product has a high mechanical strength. The effect of amount of added hydrogen peroxide on the flexural strength is shown in Fig. 17. There is a positive correlation between the amount of hydrogen peroxide and the flexural strength. However, furan resin with 4.0 g per 100 g furan resin of hydrogen peroxide or more became extremely hot and out of control during the curing process (runaway reaction). These results indicate that the optimum amount of

hydrogen peroxide to be added is 2.5-3.5 grams. Moreover, the addition of hydrogen peroxide could improve the flexural strength from 43 MPa to 125 MPa.

Fig. 16 The delamination in the composite laminates

Fig. 17 The delamination in the composite laminates

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Fig. 18 (a) The delamination in the composite laminates

Fig. 18 (b) The delamination in the composite laminates

matrix failure and (2) delamination between the fiber layer and matrix layer. The photographs of the fracture surface are shown in Fig. 20(a) and Fig. 20(b). The fracture surface of 20(a) is fairly flat; it is clear that all the fibers are cut as fractured. Fig. 20(a) indicates that the fracture energy for fiber and matrix is less than the delamination energy. On the other hand, the fracture surface of (b) has some noticeable sharpness, and shows long, prominent fibers pulled out. The observation indicates that the delamination energy is less than the fractural energy. From these results, it can be surmised that adding hydrogen peroxide probably weaken the fibers and may decrease the mechanical strength of the NFRP.

In the future, the authors will explore immersing the fibers in hydrogen peroxide and measure their strength to confirm this hypothesis, and use the result of this test to establish a new method for NFRP fabrication that will not cause fiber damage.

Fig. 19 (a) The delamination in the composite laminates

3.4.4 Mechanical strength of furan NFRP

By adding with hydrogen peroxide, the curing pure furan resin is enhanced as already mentioned. From this, the effect of adding hydrogen peroxide in furan NFRPs are determined. Fig. 20 shows a photograph of the cross-section of a furan NFRP added with hydrogen peroxide and cured with only a hot-press machine. In comparison with one shown in Fig. 13, it is observed that there is no delamination in the composite; this may be because using hot-press machine in all curing process enhances the adhesion between fiber sheets and furan matrix.

Fig. 19 shows the mechanical strength of furan NFRPs with and without the added hydrogen peroxide. The NFRP with hydrogen peroxide has a relatively higher strength (about 130 MPa); unfortunately, however, it is found to be weaker than the oven-cured sample.

When the NFRP is broken, there are two types of destruction mechanism observed: (1) fiber and

Fig. 19 (b) The effect of addition with Hydrogen peroxide

Fig. 20(a) fracture surface of NFRPs which is added hydrogen peroxide

Fig. 20(b) fracture surface of NFRPs which is added hydrogen peroxide

4 Conclusion

Furan resin is a bio-based plastic derived from agricultural product. It is a thermosetting resin, and it is therefore not biodegradable. It has a high heat resistance and high corrosion resistance. These suggest that furan NFRPs can be used in corrosion resistant tanks and are applicable in many cases that require high durability.

In fabricating a high-mechanical-property furan resin, the concentration and availability of oxygen are extremely important because furan resin need oxygen for complete curing. However, the addition of oxygen is very difficult since a thermosetting resin is usually cured in a closed system (done by hot-press machine). This problem can be solved by two methods. First method is using hot-press machine until gelation, and then afterwards cured completely with the heater oven. The optimum temperature of the oven is 115°C and at 145°C. Second method is addition of peroxide to the furan resin mixture to chemically provide the oxygen for furan resin. The mechanical strength of pure furan resin is increased significantly by adding hydrogen peroxide.

5 References

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